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DEFINING INTERESTS IN THE USE OF NATURAL ASSETS OF THE SHORELINE PROTECTION BELT IN THE CONTEXT OF BLUE GROWTH

ВИЗНАЧЕННЯ ІНТЕРЕСІВ У СФЕРІ ВИКОРИСТАННЯ ПРИРОДНИХ АКТИВІВ ПРИБЕРЕЖНОЇ ЗАХИСНОЇ СМУГИ В УМОВАХ БЛАКИТНОГО ЗРОСТАННЯ

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Сриберко А.В., Степанова Ю.В. Визначення інтересів у сфері використання природних активів прибережної захисної смуги в умовах блакитного зростання. Оглядова стаття.

Визначення інтересів у сфері використання природних активів прибережної захисної смуги в умовах блакитного зростання зумовлено перетином економічних, екологічних і соціальних аспектів. Це зростання передбачає сталий розвиток морських ресурсів, що актуалізує управління природними активами. Метою дослідження є визначення економічних, екологічних і соціальних інтересів у зазначеній сфері на основі науково-методичних підходів. Використано нормативні акти ЄС та України, наукові й аналітичні джерела. Методи: діалектичний, порівняльний, логічний аналіз. Визначено, що підходи мають міждисциплінарний характер. Інтереси стейкхолдерів залежать від типу блага, а управління активами передбачає баланс приватних і суспільних інтересів. Запропоновані підходи сприяють досягненню Цілей сталого розвитку, ефективному використанню ресурсів і формуванню стійкої екосистеми.

Ключові слова: природні активи, економічні та екологічні інтереси, соціальні інтереси, прибережні екосистеми, прибережна захисна смуга, сталий розвиток, блакитне зростання, управління, науково-методичні підходи

Sryberko A.V., Stepanova Yu.V. Defining Interests in the Use of Natural Assets of the Shoreline Protection Belt in the Context of Blue Growth. Review article.

The definition of interests in the use of natural assets of the coastal protection strip in the context of blue growth is determined by the intersection of economic, environmental, and social aspects. This growth involves the sustainable development of marine resources, which makes the management of natural assets relevant. The purpose of the study is to determine economic, environmental, and social interests in this area based on scientific and methodological approaches. EU and Ukrainian regulations, scientific and analytical sources were used. Methods: dialectical, comparative, logical analysis. It was determined that the approaches are interdisciplinary in nature. The interests of stakeholders depend on the type of benefit, and asset management requires a balance between private and public interests. The proposed approaches contribute to the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals, the efficient use of resources, and the formation of a sustainable ecosystem.

Keywords: natural assets, economic interests, ecological interests, social interests, coastal ecosystems, shoreline protection belt, sustainable development, blue growth, management, scientific and methodological approaches

Conducting research to determine interests in various spheres of human life and, in general, identifying the best conditions for the existence and development of society by using these conditions has always been conducted, is being conducted, and will be conducted in the future. Any interests are based on needs that arise in the environment among living organisms, in particular humans with the development of society over many centuries. This logical conclusion can be drawn based on the interpretation of the concept of "interest". As you know (Bazylevych, 2007), "interest" (interesse – "to have an important meaning" in Latin) is a form of expression of a need, a person's conscious desire to satisfy it.

One of the key aspects of the issue of determining economic, environmental and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth is to ensure a balance between the use of these assets for the benefit of economic development and environmental preservation. On the one hand, economic interests may represent the need to exploit coastal assets for commercial purposes (tourism, fishing, real estate construction, etc.), which may lead to increased profitability, but at the same time may have a detrimental impact on natural resources and the living space of the local population. On the other hand, environmental and social interests necessarily require the preservation of natural assets and the provision of favorable conditions for local populations, which may be vulnerable to the destruction of ecosystems and the loss of natural assets.

One important solution to this problem could be a developed management system. This system would take into account all aspects of the interests of

participants and ensure sustainable and balanced use of the natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth based on modern scientific and methodological approaches to determining economic, environmental, and social interests.

Analysis of recent research and publications

It should be noted that the types of interests we have studied in this paper in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth fully coincide with the three main dimensions of sustainable development of blue economy activities, which are based on the economic, environmental and social aspects of sustainability. (European Commission, European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency, 2021).

It is known (Das, 2023) that the term "Blue Growth" revolves around the idea of a blue economy in most literature (Mulazzani & Malorgio, 2017). The authors (Lillebø et al., 2017) argue that the blue growth agenda published by the European Commission in 2012 (European Commission, 2012) focuses on maritime economic activities. In turn, the authors (Burgess et al., 2018) view blue growth as the integrated management of complex marine social ecological systems. Approximately 1% to 5% of the gross domestic product (GDP) of many developing countries is generated by the ocean economy (Kildow & McIlgorm, 2010). According to the European Commission proposal in 2021 (European Commission, 2021), a paradigm shift from blue growth to a sustainable blue economy is essential to reduce the cumulative impact of economic activities in the ocean. According to the authors (Eikeset et al., 2018), the term "Blue Growth" does not have a clear definition and its meaning varies significantly depending on the context, region, and priorities. It has been adopted by various regional and international institutions to develop their policies on the blue economy. The author (Guerreiro, 2021) argues that the blue economy or blue growth is a system in which public policy, privatization, and scientific progress intersect, and new maritime industries become a political agenda (Van den Burg et al., 2019). The author (Sryberko, 2023) cites the European Commission's definition of the working title of the sustainable blue economy (European Commission, European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency, 2021): "A sustainable blue economy promotes economic growth, social inclusion and improved livelihoods, while ensuring the environmental sustainability of the natural capital of the oceans and seas. The blue economy encompasses all sectoral and cross-sectoral economic activities related to oceans, seas and coasts. It includes new sectors and economic value based on natural capital and non-market goods and services through the conservation of the marine environment and ecosystem services". The concepts of blue growth and blue economy also hold promise for addressing issues such as natural resource depletion and climate change by creating a new platform for minimizing environmental impacts (Bowen & Fankhauser, 2011). The author (Das, 2023) states that the main sectors of blue growth

or blue economy were initially coastal and maritime tourism, renewable energy, aquaculture, mineral extraction and biotechnology (European Commission, 2010). Then, different countries added other potential sectors, such as fisheries, marine hydrocarbons, salt, water, transportation, ship and boat building, blue biotechnology, deep-sea mining, and marine tourism (Guerreiro, 2021; Klinger et al., 2018; European Commission, 2017). The drive to explore for and extract oil, gas, minerals, proteins, and energy is putting increasing pressure on the oceans (Brent et al., 2018). The multiple uses of marine space in the form of both synergistic (e.g. renewable energy and tourism) and antagonistic (e.g. fishing and drilling) sectors (Crona et al., 2021) require "spatial efficiency" (Kyvelou & Ierapetritis, 2021). With the increase in blue economy activities and the associated challenges (Bellanger et al, 2020), researchers and policymakers are calling for better analysis of blue economy sectors (Wenhai et al., 2019). In addition, the United Nations declared the period from 2021 to 2030 as the "Decade of Ocean Science and Sustainable Development", aimed at restoring ocean health and providing a common platform for ocean stakeholders around the world (Lee et al., 2020).

Unsolved aspects of the problem

In general, it is fundamentally impossible to solve the problem of determining economic, environmental, and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth. It is only possible to study the variability of these interests taking into account the urgent needs of humanity at a certain stage of its historical development. Thus, we will list only a few areas of urgent tasks, the solutions of which contribute to the sustainability of economic development, environmental preservation, and improvement of people's livelihoods and the social well-being of communities, regions, and Ukraine as a whole. Determining economic, environmental, and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth is very relevant today. Shoreline protection belts play a crucial role in preserving biodiversity, protecting coastal areas from erosion, storms, and other natural hazards.

Determining economic interests in the mentioned area will help ensure a balance between the preservation of natural assets and the development of a blue economy based on the use of marine and coastal resources and promoting sustainable development. Economic interests can be directed towards developing tourism, increasing the income of local residents, and making efficient use of natural assets, etc.

Determining ecological interests in the mentioned area is an extremely urgent task in the modern world and consists in ensuring a balance between economic benefits from the use of natural assets and environmental protection. This will ensure sustainable development and preservation of natural assets for future generations. In general, studies by domestic and foreign scientists indicate that ecological interests are aimed at preserving biodiversity, environmental cleanliness, and preventing coastal degradation.

Determining social interests in the mentioned area is an important aspect of sustainable development. The natural assets of the shoreline protection belt play a key role in ensuring the economic and environmental sustainability of the region. In order to use these assets harmoniously, it is important to conduct research and consultations with various stakeholders, it is necessary to consider and balance the interests of different social groups, including local residents, tourists, entrepreneurs, scientists, specialists from environmental organizations and authorities in general. Social interests include improving the living conditions of local populations, preserving cultural heritage, and ensuring access to natural resources, including natural assets, for all population groups.

Thus, understanding and taking into account the above interests can help in developing an effective coastal zone management strategy and contribute to the sustainable development of the region in the context of blue growth at the regional, national and even global levels. The relevance of determining economic, environmental, and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth ensures a balance between economic development, environmental preservation, and social well-being.

Formulation of research objectives (problem statement). Determination of economic, environmental and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belts in the conditions of blue growth based on the generalization of scientific and methodological approaches was the aim of the study. The following tasks were set during the study: to form scientific and methodological approaches to determining economic, environmental and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth; to determine the interests of key stakeholders regarding the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in terms of their market distribution.

Materials and Methods. Legislative and regulatory acts in the blue economy and growth sectors of the European Union and Ukraine, domestic and foreign scientific, informational and analytical materials on the direction of blue growth, coastal strips of the seas of Ukraine were the initial information for the study. The dialectical method of scientific knowledge, comparative, logical analysis of initial information, and theoretical generalization were used in the paper.

The main part

It is known (Bazylevych, 2007) that the term "Economic interests" is the conscious desire of business entities to satisfy economic needs, which is the objective motivating motive of their economic activity. The author illustrates the relationship between needs and economic interests, which indicates that, firstly, economic interests are a form of manifestation of economic needs, secondly, they reflect a certain level and dynamics of satisfaction of economic needs, thirdly, they encourage economic entities to activities

to meet needs. Economic needs (Kravtsov, 2023) are a type of general human needs. In addition to economic needs, a person may have other types of needs: social, spiritual, the need for security, etc. The author (Kravtsov, 2023) gives an interpretation of the term "Economic interests", as, on the one hand, it is a form of expression of a need, a conscious desire of a person to satisfy it, on the other hand, it is a benefit, a benefit that is achieved in the process of implementing economic relations.

The main scientific and methodological approaches to the determination of economic interests in the field of the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the conditions of blue growth were formed by us on the basis of the analysis of modern scientific domestic and foreign bibliographic sources and scientific publications (see Table 1). The application of the approaches (Table 1) is described in sufficient detail in many bibliographic sources of information and scientific publications, which indicates their scientific validity and significance in solving scientific problems. Due to the limited scope of this article, we will provide only a few examples for the scientific justification of the application of the relevant approaches (column 3 in Table 1 and other similar tables).

In our opinion, the specified scientific and methodological approaches (Table 1) will help reveal the potential of economic development of shoreline protection belts, while ensuring nature conservation and sustainable use of natural assets in the context of blue growth.

The author (Nuzhnova, 1996) defines the term "Ecological interest" as an objectively existing special kind of attitude of a citizen to ecological needs and other ecological conditions that ensure his normal life in the surrounding natural environment. According to the author (Parfonov, 2013), ecological interests are the interests of the individual, society and the state in the field of environmental protection, rational nature management, ecological well-being and ensuring environmental safety. Also, the author (Parfonov, 2013) states that ecological interests should generally be defined as the perceived need of a person (society) to ensure healthy and safe living conditions that will contribute to the full functioning of society and the state. The author (Moroz, 2009) considers ecological interest using the term "legitimate ecological interest". According to the author (Moroz, 2009), ecological interest should be considered a legitimate ecological interest, if it is considered as a category that expresses the desire of people to preserve the proper quality of the environment, suitable for normal existence and reproduction. In this sense, ecological interest will have only a positive connotation. In the event that a person uses purely consumptive, useful properties of nature, without taking into account their exhaustiveness and without taking environmental protection, preventive, restorative measures, the initial approval of ecological interests loses its positive connotation, turning into directly economic or other types of interests.

Table 1. The main scientific and methodological approaches to the determination of economic interests in the field of use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in conditions of blue growth

Approach	Application description	Justification
Economic analysis	It includes an assessment of the economic value of the natural assets of the shoreline protection belt, in such areas as tourism, fishing, recreation, etc., as well as potential losses from pollution and environmental disasters, technogenic (anthropogenic), natural and military emergencies.	(Bubenko et al., 2014; Berenda et al., 2017; Yakymchuk et al., 2023; Dziadykevych et al., 2016)
The cost of ecosystem services	Determination of the cost of ecosystem services of the coastal zone, in particular the shoreline protection belt, for example, such as protection from natural disasters, carbon sequestration and preservation of biodiversity, populations of various species of living organisms.	(Bubenko et al., 2014; Berenda et al., 2017; Yakymchuk et al., 2023; Dehtiar, 2012; Acharya, 2000; Sotnyk & Mogilenets, 2011; Sakal, 2016; Rubel et al., 2024; Pagiola et al., 2004)
Assessment of investment attractiveness	Analysis of potential investments in the development of the infrastructure of the shoreline protection belt, for example, such as sanatoriums, hotels and other tourist and recreational facilities.	(Petrovs'ka, 2012; Petrovs'ka, 2013; Sabadash & Petrovs'ka, 2013; Umanets, 2006; Kolesnyk & Skorobohatova, 2012; Hudz, 2012)
Strategic development planning	Preparing of development strategies that would take into account the potential of economic growth, nature conservation and sustainable development of shoreline protection belts.	(Law of Ukraine, 2015)
Market research and demand analysis	Study of market trends, demand and competitiveness of natural assets and ecosystem services offered in coastal zones, particularly within the shoreline protection belt.	Martynovych et al., 2021; Roshchyna, 2015; Tendyuk, 2013; Kuchmiiiov, 2011; Starostina & Kravchenko, 2011; Barabanova, 2020; Amons & Krasnyak, 2020)
Risk assessment and risk management	Determination of potential economic risks associated with changes in the use of natural assets of the coastal protection strip and development of strategies for their management.	DSTU IEC/ISO 31010:2013, 2015; Mostenska & Skopenko, 2010; Borovyk, 2016; Dergachova & Manaenko, 2020)
Stakeholder participation	Involvement of stakeholders, including representatives of local and regional authorities, scientists, public organizations and the business environment in the process of determining economic interests and developing strategies for their implementation.	(Order Ministry for Communities and Territories Development of Ukraine, 2022)

Source: the authors' own elaboration

The main scientific and methodological approaches to the determination of ecological interests in the field of use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the conditions of blue growth were formed by us on

the basis of the analysis of modern scientific domestic and foreign bibliographic sources and scientific publications (see Table 2).

Table 2. The main scientific and methodological approaches to the determination of ecological interests in the field of use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in conditions of blue growth

Approach	Application description	Justification
Environmental modeling	Using mathematical models to predict the impact of various human activities on coastal ecosystems and their response to climate change.	Lohvinkov et al., 2017; Justic, 2016; Itoh et al., 2018, 2024; Sohma et al., 2018; Testa & Justic, 2024; Sryberko & Stepanova, 2024)
Environmental monitoring	Systematic observation and assessment of the condition of natural assets, including water and biological resources that are components of the shoreline protection belt, as well as the shoreline protection belt itself in the context of the natural asset.	(Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2024)
Assessment of ecosystem services	Determination and valuing the cost of ecosystem services of the coastal zone, in particular the shoreline protection belt, for example, such as protection from natural disasters, water filtration, biodiversity, etc.	(Petrovs'ka, 2012; Petrovs'ka, 2013; Sabadash & Petrovs'ka, 2013; Umanets, 2006; Kolesnyk & Skorobohatova, 2012; Hudz, 2012)
Impact assessment of projects and activities	Analysis of the impact of various projects and activities on the ecological state of the shoreline protection belt, including risk assessment and development of measures to minimize negative impacts.	(Law of Ukraine, 2015, 2017, 2018)
Conservation and recovery strategies	Development of strategies for the preservation and restoration of coastal ecosystems, including the creation of protected and reserved areas, and wetland restoration programs of national and international importance.	(Order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2021; Sryberko et al., 2023)
Taking into account the principles of sustainable use of natural resources	Determination of opportunities for economic activity that would not harm coastal ecosystems and ensure their sustainability in the long term.	(Decree of the President of Ukraine, 2019)
Public and expert engagement	Taking into account the opinions of environmental experts and active public participation in the decision-making process regarding the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt.	(Law of Ukraine, 2017, 2018)

Source: the authors' own elaboration

The above scientific and methodological approaches take into account ecological interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt and contribute to the development of balanced use not only of the natural assets of the coastal zone, but also of the coastal part of the sea, ensuring the preservation of ecosystems and supporting their sustainability in the context of blue growth.

The author (Clark, 2017) states that the term "Social interest", introduced in the early 1900s by Alfred Adler, refers to a person's kinship with other living beings and a sense of belonging to the human community (Adler, 1964). Alfred Adler also defined social interest as an orientation toward cooperation between individuals or as a way of life that implies a greater value for the common good than for individual interests and desires. At the heart of social interest is a sense of community, that is, an innate ability to identify with other people, ultimately with all of humanity, viewing the problems faced by the majority as no different from one's own (Sydorkina, 2019). In sociology (Herasymchuk et al., 2004), the term "social interest" is defined as: "one of the most important driving forces of the behavior and activity of any social subject, individual, social community, stratum, society». In turn, the author (Tikhonovich, 2010) defines the term "social interest" as: "the rational-value position of a subject (individual / personality / group / community) regarding the provision (preservation / reproduction / improvement / development) of the conditions and methods of their life activity and behavior in society". The paper (Lyuta, 2019) states that social interest is a form in which an individual or

social group is directly aware of their real situation and their needs, which are expressed in the form of goals that the individual sets for himself. Also, according to the author (Lyuta, 2019), social interest is: "the true, real reason for social actions, which arises from the motives and thoughts of the participants in these actions". In turn, lawyers (Drobush, 2015) believe that social interests are based on the principles of social justice, equality, and freedom and aim at a general increase in well-being, which is possible only through the implementation of socio-economic rights, which will ultimately guarantee a decent living wage and certain types of social security. According to the author (Drobush, 2015): "the fundamental principle of the implementation of social interests is social humanism, aimed at creating conditions and mechanisms to ensure a decent life for citizens, social protection, minimizing social risks, as well as creating conditions for the self-realization of the potential of each representative of the relevant territorial community, thereby ensuring the further development of Ukraine as a social state with a developed civil society". The author (Osadchuk, 2023) emphasizes that the term "social interest" refers to aspects related to issues of social well-being and the quality of human life.

The main scientific and methodological approaches to the determination of social interests in the field of use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the conditions of blue growth were formed by us on the basis of the analysis of numerous modern scientific domestic and foreign bibliographic sources and scientific publications (see Table 3).

Table 3. The main scientific and methodological approaches to the determination of social interests in the field of use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in conditions of blue growth

Approach	Application description	Justification
Sociological research	Conducting surveys, focus groups, and other sociological methods to study the opinions, needs, and demands of the local population regarding the use of the shoreline protection belt.	(Dvoretzka, 2002; Mykhailych, 2010; Danylian & Dzoban, 2019)
Stakeholder analysis and public participation	Identifying and involving various stakeholders, such as local residents, local governments, and community organizations, in the decision-making process regarding the use of coastal assets.	Myroshnychenko & Bondar, 2018; Potii, 2022; Kovalevska & Zelenskiy, 2019; Savage et al., 1991)
Social benefit assessment	Analysis of potential social benefits from the development of tourism, fishing, recreation and other activities in the coastal zone.	(Morozova, 2019)
Taking into account the needs of the local community	Taking into account the cultural, historical and social characteristics of local communities in the planning and implementation of coastal zone use projects.	(Decision of the Odessa Regional Council, 2020; Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2020)
Principles of cooperation and social responsibility	Involving businesses and other stakeholders in socially responsible projects aimed at improving the well-being of local communities and preserving the environment.	(Law of Ukraine, 2014; Okhrimenko & Ivanova, 2015; DSTU ISO 26000:2019, 2020).
Infrastructure and service development	Ensuring access to education, healthcare, recreational infrastructure and other social services for the local population in the coastal area.	(Bliznyuk, 2019)
Consensus decisions and partnerships	Collaboration between government, public and private sectors to build consensus and address social issues in coastal areas.	(Didyk, 2007; Decision of the Odessa Regional Council, 2020; Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2020)

Source: the authors' own elaboration

Thus, the above approaches help ensure that the social interests of the local population of coastal regions are taken into account and their well-being is

preserved when using the natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth.

Generalizing the results of the analysis of scientific and methodological approaches to determining econo-

mic, environmental and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth, it can be stated that these

approaches combine scientific, methodological and practical aspects. Let's form the main generalized scientific and methodological approaches in Table 4.

Table 4. Generalized scientific and methodological approaches to determining economic, ecological and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth

Approach	Description
Interdisciplinary research.	Provide analysis of economic, ecological and social aspects of the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt. This includes economic models to assess the profitability of projects, ecological assessments of environmental impacts, and sociological studies of the impact on the local community.
Stakeholder analysis.	Identifying stakeholders in the shoreline protection belt area and taking their needs and views into account when formulating strategies for the use of natural assets.
Sustainable development concept.	The use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt should be based on the principles of economic efficiency, environmental sustainability and social justice to ensure long-term sustainability.
Cost-benefit analysis methods.	Assessment of the economic value of natural assets and the benefits from their use, including methods for assessing economic impact, the cost of ecosystem services, etc.
Economic incentives for sustainable use of natural assets.	Development of incentive programs, such as environmental payments, lending under the conditions of sustainable use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt, which contribute to reducing negative impacts and supporting sustainable development.
Risk management and climate change adaptation.	Developing strategies for climate change adaptation and coastal risk management that take into account economic, environmental and social aspects.
Public participation and communication.	Involving the public in the process of resolving issues related to the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt through the development of communication channels and feedback mechanisms.

Source: the authors' own elaboration

Thus, the above scientific and methodological approaches aim to ensure a balance between economic needs, ecosystem preservation, and satisfaction of social interests regarding the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth. By combining these approaches, decision-makers can make informed choices that balance economic development with environmental conservation and social well-being.

Despite the relevance of sustainable development of coastal and marine areas, they face increasing rates of degradation caused by a wide variety of factors and stakeholder groups that demand different types of goods and services provided by the ecosystems of these areas.

The degradation of ecosystems and the depletion of their services can be explained by private exploitation at scales that are not socially optimal from an economic perspective. Economic theory suggests that markets allocate scarce resources efficiently. Under certain conditions, markets would allow for optimal allocation: first, there must be many buyers and many sellers of a good or service; second, any person participating in the market is free to enter or leave it at any time; third, adequate information about the good or service must be available, including all benefits or costs that access to it may entail; fourth, the rights to use and exploit that good or service must be clearly defined and well known; and fifth, the use and exploitation of the good or service must not create externalities for others outside the market. A market is defined as perfectly competitive and efficient in terms of resource allocation when these conditions are met (Maldonado et al., 2020).

However, for many ecosystem services, there are no markets in which they can be traded. Even when an ecosystem service is traded on a market, some of the above conditions may not be met. Ecosystem services

provided by marine and coastal zones are characterized by the presence of many market failures, such as the lack of clearly defined property rights, the existence of externalities, and the presence of asymmetric information.

Any good or service, including natural assets, can be characterized by two basic properties: exclusion and rivalry in consumption. Excludability concerns to the extent to which it is possible to decide who benefits from access to a product or service and who does not. If it is impossible to determine who has access to a product or service (or to prevent individual users from accessing it), the product is said to be non-excludable. What determines whether a product is excludable is the marginal cost associated with creating such an exclusion; the higher the cost, the more difficult it will be to make the product exclusive. Excludability is closely related to the concept of property rights. Property rights are defined as powers that can be enforced and that can be granted to a person, group of people, or the state to perform certain actions in a specific area (Ostrom & Schlager, 1996). The excludability will be valid when the property rights can be easily divided and the division of rights can be enforced. However, many ecosystem services, such as coastal protection, are non-excludable because access to them is free. This is the main reason for their insufficient provision and overexploitation.

Rivalry refers to the relationship between the consumption of a good or service by an individual and the possibility of its simultaneous consumption by other individuals. The cost of providing a good to another person is zero when it is non-rivalrous.

The combination of the properties of rivalry and excludability allows us to characterize natural assets in the context of the market for goods and services (see Figure 1), namely.

Figure 1. Classification of natural assets according to the properties of goods and services

Source: the authors' own elaboration

Private goods are rival and excludable. This means that the use of a natural asset by one person reduces its availability to others, and people may be deprived of access to that asset. An example of the private goods of the coastal belt can be:

- areas of land on the seashore, whose landowners have exclusive access to their land, and other people may be excluded from accessing them or using their space, for example to obtain positive impressions;
- private fish farms or shellfish and seaweed farming on the coast, where a company or individual has exclusive rights to grow and catch marine hydrobionts in a designated area.

Club goods have low rivalry, but easy exclusion. This means that people may be excluded from using a natural asset, but the use of that asset by one person does not reduce its availability to others, at least to a certain capacity. An example of the club goods of the coastal belt can be:

- private beach clubs that provide exclusive access to a part of the beach, members of which pay for admission or membership. The beach itself is a natural resource, but access to it is controlled, and use by club members does not necessarily reduce the quality of access for other club members;
- coastal resorts and hotels built along the coast offer a range of services (e.g. swimming pools, private beaches, amenities) that are only available to guests or visitors. Ecosystem services (e.g., beach access, ocean views) are non-rivalrous to guests or visitors, but are excludable to those outside the resort or hotel;
- private excursions (eco-tourism tours) of coastal ecosystems (e.g. dolphin watching or scuba diving

excursions) in which a small group of participants share impressions. Participation in the tour is not available to persons who have not paid for it, however, the actual impression cannot be reduced due to the number of participants up to a certain limit.

Public goods are non-rivalrous and non-excludable. This means that no one can be excluded from using the asset, and the use of the asset by one person does not reduce its availability to others. These goods are usually provided or protected by governments or public institutions. An example of the public goods of the coastal belt can be:

- clean air and scenic views, i.e. coastal areas in their majority provide public access to clean air, sea breezes and the natural beauty of the coast. They are non-rivalrous and non-excludable. Everyone can enjoy these benefits without diminishing the ability of others to do the same;
- public beaches, meaning most of the coast, especially in public areas, are open to everyone without restrictions. One person's use of the beach does not reduce the ability of others to use it, at least to some extent, and no one may be deprived of access to it;
- marine and coastal ecosystem services: the benefits provided by coastal ecosystems, such as shorelines, wetlands, and seaweed, are public goods. They provide important ecosystem services such as coastal protection from storms and floods, carbon sequestration and absorption, and habitat for marine hydrobionts and coastal biodiversity. These services are not diminished by one person's use of them, and it is difficult to exclude anyone from using them.

Common-pool resources have high rivalry and difficult exclusion of consumers. This means that people can use a natural asset, but its use by one person reduces the availability of that asset to others. However, it is difficult or even impossible to prevent people from accessing or using the relevant natural asset. This often leads to its overexploitation and depletion, as the total amount extracted exceeds the effective and sustainable use (Ostrom & Schlager, 1996). This phenomenon was first identified by Garrett Hardin in 1968 (Hardin, 1968) as the "tragedy of the commons". It is an example of how the lack of ownership rights to a competing good lead to overexploitation, very low efficiency, and a critical situation for both the asset itself and those who benefit from it. A typical example of a common-pool resource of a coastal belt can be:

- fisheries, i.e. coastal fisheries, are mostly a common-pool resource. Fish and other marine hydrobionts in the wild are rivals, meaning that, for example, if one person catches a fish, it is no longer available to other people, but it is difficult to prohibit people from fishing in public waters, meaning that they cannot be excluded.
- freshwater resources in coastal regions, such as aquifers or rivers flowing into the sea, can be a common-pool resource. While individual access to groundwater can be regulated, overuse by one party can impact availability for others, especially in water-scarce regions.
- coastal sand and minerals (e.g. for building). In some cases, sand and minerals extracted from coastal areas, especially if extraction is not properly regulated, can be common-pool resources. They are rivals (over-exploitation can lead to depletion or degradation), but it can be difficult to exclude people from using them, especially in poorly regulated areas.

In general, most ecosystem services provided by marine and coastal areas, including shorelines, are either public goods or common-pool resources. Given that there are no consumer exclusions for public goods, it is difficult to transfer ownership rights, and therefore markets are not an efficient mechanism for allocating such resources. In particular, since exclusion is not possible, people will be tempted to use them without

paying for their consumption, and since there is no way to exclude consumers who do not pay, there will be fewer people in the market willing to pay than expected. This ability of consumers not paying for the provision of goods or services they use is known as the free-rider problem. (Glover, 2010). This problem is that the government often provides public goods. On the other hand, the fact that a good is provided by the state does not necessarily mean that it has the economic characteristics of a public good. While the government cannot make a good exclusive in the literal sense, it can finance public goods by levying taxes on those who benefit from the good and then offering the goods at zero price. The government's decision about whether to fund a public good is based on whether the benefits to society from consuming the good outweigh the costs to society of taxing it (including the irreversible payments caused by the tax). Regulatory services, such as coastal protection, are prone to excludability and rivalrous properties. This is usually for the public good, meaning that not many people are interested in paying to support their provision. An example of this situation is the high level of degradation of coastal ecosystems due to human activities (Barbier et al., 2011).

Thus, based on the above, it becomes possible to identify key stakeholders. After all, it is their interests that are fully aimed at preserving the natural assets of coastal belts, their sustainable development, and effective management of coastal belts in general.

We will identify key stakeholders taking into account the criteria of the Mendelow model (Mendelow's Matrix). That is, key stakeholders have the highest level of desire and ability to influence projects for the protection and restoration of natural assets, their sustainable development, and effective management of coastal belts in general. In turn, this will allow for the development of balanced strategies that promote sustainable development, reduce environmental risks, effectively use natural assets, and enhance social cohesion. All of this is certainly the key to successful and long-term management of these important natural areas. Let's form a distribution of key stakeholders and their interests in the context of the use of natural assets of coastal belts in accordance with the categories of goods involved, which we have given above (see Table 5).

Table 5. Distribution of key stakeholders and their interests in the context of the use of natural assets of coastal belts

Goods	Key stakeholders	Interests
1	2	3
Private goods	Private property owners (landowners, business owners, etc.)	Seek to maximize the value of their land or property by using it for personal or commercial purposes. Their main interest is in exclusivity and protection of their property rights. This allows them to control access and profit from coastal assets.
	Developers and investors	First of all, they are interested in building on coastal land, especially in tourist hotspots, resorts, recreational areas or for real estate. Their interest is aimed at making a profit by selling or renting land and property in the coastal belt area.
	Local communities	They may be stakeholders in terms of property rights or access to private goods. But they may be marginalized if their access to these private goods is restricted.
Club goods	Resort and beach club owners	They benefit from providing exclusive access to a limited number of individuals or a group of individuals, providing high-quality environmental (nature) impressions.
	Members of exclusive clubs	Interested in ensuring quality and exclusivity of access. These stakeholders may insist on regulation, that is, limiting access by outsiders, to preserve the value of their membership.

Continuation of Table 5

1	2	3
Club goods	Local governments, tourism authorities	Interested in promoting tourism while balancing private access with broader public interests, such as preserving the natural beauty of coastal belts.
Public goods	Local communities	Interested in preserving access to public goods such as beaches and the overall environmental quality of coastal belts.
	Ecological non-governmental organizations	Focused on preserving ecosystems and biodiversity. Their interest lies in ensuring the sustainable management of natural assets to avoid their overexploitation or degradation.
	Government (local, regional and national)	Typically, responsible for managing and protecting public goods, balancing economic development (e.g. tourism and recreation) with environmental preservation and sustainable development.
	Tourists	Stakeholders as users of public beaches and other public coastal belts. Tourist interests are focused on preserving the natural beauty and accessibility of coastal regions' shorelines.
Common-pool resources	Fishermen	Concerned about maintaining healthy fish stocks. Because overfishing can deplete these resources. Their interest lies in sustainable fishing practices and fair access to fish resources.
	Government (local, regional and national)	The government is tasked with managing common-pool resources to prevent their overuse and depletion. Its interests lie in preserving the resource base for future generations while ensuring economic stability, for example in sectors such as fishing and tourism.
	Ecologists	Concerned about protecting coastal ecosystems, such as shorelines, which are common-pool resources and offer benefits such as protection from storms and floods and biodiversity. Their interest lies in maintaining the ecological health of coastal belts, which benefits both human communities and wildlife.
	Tourists	Tourists do not usually directly use common-pool resources, but they may have an indirect interest in the health of coastal ecosystems, especially from the perspective of sustainable tourism that does not degrade the environment.
	Locals	These stakeholders often rely on coastal ecosystems for food, livelihoods, and cultural customs. Their interests include preserving access to common-pool resources, ensuring that these resources are not depleted through overuse.

Source: the authors' own elaboration

It would also be logical to note that conflicts of interest and, conversely, their synergy arise between key stakeholders. Balancing the needs of different stakeholders is a key issue in the management of natural assets of coastlines. For example, private developers may prioritize maximizing profits from beachfront real estate, while environmentalists may advocate for the preservation of natural coastal ecosystems, particularly shorelines. Similarly, overfishing by commercial fishermen can deplete common-pool resources, harming both local communities and the biodiversity of those resources. Regarding the synergy of interests of key stakeholders, it can be noted that sustainable practices can create it. For example, ecotourism can contribute to the conservation of coastal ecosystems while benefiting the local economy. Collaboration between government, environmental NGOs, and local communities can help protect common-pool resources while ensuring equitable access for all stakeholders.

In our opinion, an algorithm for determining the interests of key stakeholders regarding in the use of natural assets of the coastal belt may include the following steps:

1. Identification of key stakeholders with an interest in the natural assets of the coastal belt.
2. Conducting an analysis of the interests of each stakeholder, including their needs, goals, perspectives, and priorities regarding the natural assets of the coastal belt.
3. Establishing mechanisms to involve stakeholders in the process of identifying interests, such as public consultations, surveys, working groups, etc.
4. Analysis of the data obtained and development of a strategy for taking into account the interests of

various stakeholders when making decisions regarding the management of natural assets of the coastal belt.

5. Continuous monitoring and updating of information on stakeholder interests to ensure reliable and effective the management of natural assets of the coastal belt.

Thus, stakeholders' interests in natural assets in the shoreline protection belt depend largely on the type of good in question. Managing these assets typically involves balancing private interests with public goods and ensuring the sustainable use of common-pool resources to avoid their overexploitation and depletion.

Conclusion

As a result of the research, the following generalizing conclusions can be drawn.

In our opinion, the scientific and methodological approaches formed in this paper to determine economic, environmental, and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth in the complex are interdisciplinary in nature and include a number of aspects. From an economic perspective, opportunities for the development of tourism and recreation, fishing, renewable energy, blue biotechnology, and other industries that can generate revenue for the region should be considered. It is important to keep in mind a balanced approach to avoid negative impacts on nature and the local environment. It is also important to consider environmental sustainability and conservation aspects when developing strategies for the use of coastal assets. Another important aspect is taking into account the social needs of the local population and ensuring their participation in decision-making. In general, the scientific and methodological approaches

presented in the paper contribute to ensuring the sustainable use of the natural assets of the shoreline protection belt, taking into account all economic, environmental, and social aspects.

Of course, experts from various fields of knowledge may have suggestions for expanding the list of scientific and methodological approaches we have provided. In our opinion, this paper has formed a "solid foundation" of scientific and methodological approaches that comprehensively take into account economic, environmental, and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth. They also contribute to the achievement of the sustainable development goals, in

particular Goal 13 – Climate Action, Goal 14 – Life Below Water, Goal 15 – Life on Land, and the implementation of strategies and plans aimed at the conservation and sustainable use of natural assets and ecosystems.

In general, a deep understanding of the interests of key stakeholders in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt allows for the development of balanced strategies that promote sustainable development, reduce environmental risks, efficiently use natural assets, and enhance social cohesion, helping to create a sustainable and win-win ecosystem, which is a necessary condition for the effective management of these resources in the long term.

Abstract

Topicality. The definition of interests in the use of natural assets of the coastal buffer strip in the context of blue growth is determined by key factors that intersect with economic, environmental, and social aspects. Blue growth involves the sustainable development of marine and coastal resources to ensure economic growth, ecosystem sustainability and social well-being. It prioritizes the management of natural assets, including coastal ecosystems. The relevance of identifying interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belts is extremely high in the context of blue growth. After all, it provides for a balanced approach to addressing economic, environmental, and social challenges, which will ensure the sustainable development of coastal regions in the future.

Aim and tasks. Determination of economic, environmental and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belts in the conditions of blue growth based on the generalization of scientific and methodological approaches was the aim of the study.

Materials and Methods. Legislative and regulatory acts in the blue economy and growth sectors of the European Union and Ukraine, domestic and foreign scientific, informational and analytical materials on the direction of blue growth, coastal strips of the seas of Ukraine were the initial information for the study. The dialectical method of scientific knowledge, comparative, logical analysis of initial information, and theoretical generalization were used in the paper.

Research results. The results of the study to determine economic, environmental and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belts in the context of blue growth, taking into account the established generalized scientific and methodological approaches was described in this paper. It has been determined that the integrated application of the approaches specified in this paper is interdisciplinary in nature and includes a number of economic, environmental, and social aspects. It is argued that the interests of key stakeholders regarding natural assets in the shoreline protection belt depend largely on the type of relevant good. The management of these assets typically involves balancing private interests with public goods and ensuring the sustainable use of common resources to avoid their overexploitation and depletion.

Conclusion. The scientific and methodological approaches formed in the paper are a "solid foundation" that comprehensively takes into account economic, environmental and social interests in the use of natural assets of the shoreline protection belt in the context of blue growth. They also contribute to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals and the implementation of strategies and plans aimed at the conservation and sustainable use of natural assets and ecosystems. In general, a deep understanding of the interests of key stakeholders in the use of coastal natural assets allows for the development of balanced strategies that promote sustainable development, reduce environmental risks, efficiently use resources, and enhance social cohesion, helping to create a sustainable and win-win ecosystem, which is a necessary condition for the effective management of these resources in the long term.

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